
ISLAMIC JURISPRUDENCE ON LGBTQ+ ISSUES: LEGAL POSITIONS AND SOCIETAL IMPLICATIONS**By:****Maisuna M. Yahya-PhD**yasminmaisuna06@gmail.com

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Abstract

In modern discourse, Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, transgender, Queer/Questioning and other identities not listed (LGBTQ+) have become a matter of concerns and very central to ethical, legal and sociopolitical challenges, in Nigerian/African societies; by extension, in the global world. Islam however addresses these matters through the lens of moral acts rather than identities. This paper provides a detailed scholarly analysis of the position of Islamic Jurisprudence on LGBTQ+ identities and homosexual practices. Classical jurisprudence categorizes homosexual acts as *Liwāt* (male-male intercourse) and *Siḥāq* (female-female acts) which are considered major sins (*kaḅā'ir*) in Islamic law (*Shari'ah*). Islam emphasizes the prohibition of physical acts and public normalization. The paper identifies that this problem of LGBTQ+ is rampant among youths and as well some adults. In carrying out this research, qualitative research method, using relevant research literature works was adopted. This paper analyzes primary sources, discusses juristic consensus and explores the broader societal implications of these prohibitions. The study also explores ethical reasoning, social consequences and legal implications within Islamic law. By distinguishing between sexual inclination and acts, the paper further demonstrates how Islamic teachings uphold moral guidance and strict adherence to Islamic principles. A conclusion was drawn on the fact that LGBTQ+ practices is totally condemned by Islamic law both in the Qur'an and Hadith as capital punishments are attached to them. Thereafter, some recommendations were made.

Keywords: Islamic Jurisprudence, LGBTQ+, Implications, *Shari'ah*, capital punishments**Introduction**

In the recent years, discussions around sexual orientation, gender identity and LGBTQ+ rights have become center of tough argument to global moral, political and human rights. While many contemporary societies are moving toward legalizing and socially integrating LGBTQ+ identities and practices, Islam maintains a moral worldview grounded in the Qur'an, the Sunnah of Prophet Muhammad (SAW) and the extensive body of classical juristic scholarship developed over more than fourteen centuries. Islamic law (*Shari'ah*) approaches the question not from the lens of modern or western world's view or proposition; but from the perspective of actions, moral conduct and divine prescriptions regarding human behaviour.

The term LGBTQ+ has become one of the most widely discussed identities and social categories in contemporary global discourse. It encompasses a broad range of gender identities, sexual orientations, and experiences. Understanding the meaning, history, evolution and implications of LGBTQ+ identities is therefore crucial for academic, legal, sociological, and religious discussions.

The term LGBTQ+ was not coined by a single person but it is a gradually developed acronym that evolved over time through activism and social movements especially from the late 20th Century onwards. The acronyms are explained below:

L – Lesbian: Women who experience emotional or romantic attraction to other women (GLAAD 14).

G – Gay: Commonly refers to men attracted to men, but sometimes used as an umbrella term for same-sex attraction (Human Rights Campaign 7).

B – Bisexual: Individuals attracted to more than one gender (APA 2021).

T – Transgender: People whose gender identity does not correspond with their birth-assigned sex (Butler 33).

Q – Queer/Questioning: Queer was historically a slur but has been reclaimed by many as a broad identity category. Questioning refers to individuals exploring their sexual orientation or gender identity (GLAAD 18).

+ (Plus): Represents additional identities such as intersex, asexual, pansexual, nonbinary, and others (HRC Foundation 12).

Early Western societies such as ancient Greece had models of same-sex relationships although these were structured differently from modern sexual identity categories (Dover 52). The idea of “sexual orientation” as a fixed identity emerged only in the late 19th century particularly after the work of psychologists like Krafft-Ebing and Havelock Ellis (Foucault 43). The modern LGBTQ+ rights movement grew significantly after events like the Stonewall Riots of 1969 in New York which are widely considered a turning point in the fight against institutional discrimination (Duberman 101).

Components of LGBTQ+ Identity are three in total and includes Sexual orientation which refers to patterns of emotional, romantic, or sexual attraction toward others. Major categories include Heterosexual, Homosexual, Bisexual, Asexual and Pansexual. The American Psychological Association (APA) in 2021 emphasizes that sexual orientation is not a “choice” but arises from complex biological and environmental factors.

Gender identity is a deeply felt internal experience of gender. Categories include Cisgender, Transgender, Nonbinary and Gender-fluid. Gender identity is distinct from biological sex which refers to chromosomes, reproductive organs and other physical traits (WHO 2020) and Gender Expression which refers to how individuals present their gender through behaviour, clothing, voice or mannerisms (Butler 34).

Many Western societies have moved toward legal recognition of LGBTQ+ rights including marriage equality, anti-discrimination laws and gender recognition policies (UN Free & Equal 2020). In several African and Asian countries, LGBTQ+ identities remain socially sensitive or legally restricted due to cultural, religious or colonial legal histories (Epprecht 25). Major psychological bodies such as the American Psychiatric Association, American Psychological Association and World Health Organization state that LGBTQ+ identities are not mental illnesses and should not be treated as such according to APA in 2021 and WHO in 2020.

LGBTQ+ is an umbrella term describing identities related to sexual orientation, gender identity and gender expression. Its evolution reflects complex historical, social, scientific and political developments. Understanding LGBTQ+ concepts requires interdisciplinary study that considers biology, psychology, sociology, culture and global human rights narratives. As discussions continue, societies across the world, grapple with balancing cultural values, individual’s rights and social cohesion.

Historically, pre-modern Muslim scholars did not possess the modern conceptual frameworks of “sexual orientation, gender identity or LGBTQ+ categories.” Instead, they employed terms such as *Liwāt* (male-male sexual penetration), *Sihāq* (female-female sexual rubbing), *Ubnah* (effeminacy in males) and *Sihhah* (affective love between same-sex individuals without sexual expression). Bouhdiba (30-35,101-110), in the same manner shows that classical Islamic texts discuss sexual acts and moral regulation rather than the identity. Ali similarly maintains that pre modern Islamic jurists did not conceptualises sexuality as identity-based categories, instead, they treated issues like same-sex acts through legal rulings on behaviour, without assuming a stable sexual orientation or personal identity (78-85;101-105). The distinction is crucial as Islamic law addresses specific acts but it does not condemn individuals merely for experiencing inclinations unless those inclinations are acted upon in ways prohibited by Allah’s Divine Law.

The aim of this paper is therefore not to stigmatize, mock or dehumanize anyone but to present an academically rigorous examination of the Islamic legal position regarding LGBTQ+ identities and homosexual behavior based on revealed texts, classical juristic consensus and contemporary

scholarly interpretations. The paper also examines the social, ethical and legal implications of these practices in Muslim societies including Nigeria.

In modern discourse, LGBTQ+ identities have become central to ethical, legal and sociopolitical debates. Islam, however addresses these matters through the lens of moral acts rather than identities. Classical jurisprudence categorizes homosexual acts as *Liwāt* (male-male intercourse) and *siḥāq* (female-female acts) which are considered major sins (*kabā'ir*) in the *Shari'ah* (Ibn Kathīr 2001). While inclinations are not sinful, Islam emphasizes the prohibition of physical acts and public normalization.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Islamic legal rulings are basically derived from the primary sources of Islam (Qur'an and Hadith, while they could be supported, by the secondary sources, especially with consensus of Islamic jurists' opinions (*Ijm'a*), analogical deduction (*Qiyas*), and by extension, *Ijtihad*. Islamic framework on Ethics and moral serve as the bane of discussion in the literature review against the background on the issue of LGBTQ+. It is agreed by all classical Islamic jurists of Sunni schools that same-sex sexual acts fall outside the permissible bounds of Islamic law, as lawful sexual relations are restricted to heterosexual marriage (Rehma & Polymenopoulou 2013). Some countries of the world have legalized some of the LGBTQ+. For example, same-sex marriage was legalized in eleven countries, between 2001-2010 among them are: Netherlands, Belgium, Spain, Argentina etc. Between 2012 and 2018, fourteen countries joined the queue amongst which are Brazil, France, New Zealand and others. Islam therefore frowns at any immoral or unethical acts and provides legal means of establishing human relationship through opposite sex marriage (man and woman only) in order to preserve human lineage and heritage Kugle (2010) observes that classical Islamic jurisprudence consistently treats same-sex sexual acts under the specific legal categories such as *Liwa t* (anal intercourse between men and *Sihaq*; sexual relation between women. Rehma & Polymenopoulou (2013) maintain that classical Islamic law generally prohibits same-sex acts ... An-Na'im (1990) reiterated that Islamic law historically constructed and therefore open to reform, arguing that contemporary human rights norms, including those relating to sexual minorities should inform modern interpretations of *Shari'ah*. An-Na'im's submission here is against the Islamic principle on formation of a family, in that Allah categorically states that He created for men mates, and in them tranquility is found, to love first and procreate. Allah says:

And among His signs is that He created for you from yourself, mates that you may find tranquility in them; and He placed them between you, affection and mercy. Indeed, in that are signs for a people who reflect (Q30:21).

Above all, Islam is not open to any reform that corrupts Muslim or human ethical and moral standards; neither does it accept norms that vitiate discipline acts. Perpetually, more interpretations that will deform, bastardise, corrupt, distort, degrade and return Muslims to new era of barbaric (*Jaahiliyyah*) must be vehemently peacefully rejected, in which, LGBTQ+ are a sample at hand.

Under normal circumstance, men do not carry a pregnancy in their womb; rather it is women's exclusive duty which is not naturally biologically transferred to men. Allah says:

And We have enjoyed upon men (care) for his parents. His mother carried him, in weakness upon weakness, and his weaning is in two years.... (Q31:14). In this same vein, in Q46:15, He buttresses further:

His mother carried him with hardship and gave birth to him with hardship....

ISLAMIC SCRIPTURAL FOUNDATIONS SURROUNDING LGBTQ+

The foundational source of Islamic law is the Qur'an. A comprehensive analysis of Qur'anic evidence regarding homosexual acts reveals a consistent condemnation of the behavior particularly through the narrative of Prophet Lūṭ (Lot) and his people.

Allah says in (Q7:80–81):

And Lot, when he said to his people: "Do you commit such an immorality as no people in the world have ever committed before you? Truly you approach men with desire instead of women. Nay, you are a people exceeding all bounds."

Classical scholars like Ibn Kathir say "*Al-fāḥishah*" refers specifically to male-male sexual intercourse while the phrase "*mā sabaqakum bihā*" shows it was a historically unprecedented act indicating its deviation from natural disposition (*fiṭrah*). "*Shahwah*" (desire) confirms it was consensual, lust-driven not rape alone disproving modern reinterpretations and "*Musrifūn*" means they exceeded moral and natural boundaries as their sin was not limited to aggression but included public normalization. These verses have informed juristic rulings across Sunni and Shi'i schools (Al-Qurtubī 20).

Q27:54–55: "*And [remember] Lot when he said to his people, "Do you approach men with lust instead of women? No, you are a people acting ignorantly."*

This verse explicitly condemns homosexual acts framing them as moral ignorance. Classical scholars note that this verse alone is sufficient to establish prohibition (Al-Qurtubī 21).

Q11:78–79: "*His people came rushing toward him while before this they had been doing evil deeds. He said, "O my people, here are my daughters; they are purer for you. So fear Allah and do not disgrace me regarding my guests. Is there not among you a single right-minded man?"*

Offering his daughters demonstrates the lawful heterosexual alternative while the Qur'anic narrative portrays homosexual desire as deliberate violation of purity and divine guidance according to (Ibn Kathīr 200).

Q54:33–35: *“Indeed, We sent upon them a storm of stones, except the family of Lot; we saved them at dawn as a favor from Us. Thus do we reward those who give thanks.”*

Repeated divine punishment demonstrates severity. Classical tafsīr links it to moral corruption and public normalization of prohibited acts (Al-Rāzī 310).

Q29:28–29 condemns immorality and public evil linking homosexuality to societal corruption. Recurrent narrative emphasizes both private immorality and public consequences.

Islamic law takes its second source from the Sunnah. Although hadiths on homosexual acts vary in strength, several are authentic and classical jurists treated them collectively as authoritative.

In a Hadith narrated by Al-Tirmidhī in his book, *Sunan al-Tirmidhī* 1456 which reads : *“If you find anyone doing the act of the people of Lot then kill the one who does it and the one to whom it is done.”*

This hadith establishes moral severity as legal enforcement is restricted by strict evidentiary requirements according to (Al-Shawkānī 97) in his commentary on the hadith.

In another Hadith which addressed the LGBTQ+ issue from the point of Gender Imitation and expression narrated by (Ṣaḥīḥ al-Bukhārī 5885) who said that the *“The Prophet (SAW) cursed men who imitate women and women who imitate men.”*

The Hadith was discussed by (Ibn Ḥajar 40) on the prohibition of Female-Female Acts (Siḥāq) and confirms lesbian acts as sinful. Classical jurists classify it as morally prohibited without a fixed ḥadd. He also defined Siḥāq (female-female sexual acts) as the adultery of women among themselves.

In another narration reported by Ibn ‘Abbās that: *“The most detested of deeds to Allah, Mighty and Majestic is the act of the people of Lot.”* This Hadith emphasizes exceptional moral gravity and is used as a key source for classical legal rulings according to (Al-Shawkānī 210)

All Sunni madhāhib and Ja‘fari Shi‘a scholars classify male-male and female-female acts as prohibited. Punishments differ by school for instance; Hanafī say it is Punishable by Ta‘zīr (discretionary punishment). No fixed ḥadd. Maliki Liwāṭ is treated like adultery; ḥadd punishment may apply. Shafī‘I majority treat it as adultery with capital punishment possible if established. Hanbali school prescribes death; others ta‘zīr and Ja‘fari Shi‘I generally prescribe capital punishment under strict conditions. They all agree that inclinations without acts are not sinful, they emphasis on privacy, mercy and counseling over punitive enforcement according to (Al-Nawawī 350).

The Qur'an describes the people of Lūṭ in several chapters including Q7, Q11, Q15, Q21, Q27, Q54 and Q29. The consistency across these chapters underscores the gravity of their actions and the moral framework through which the Qur'an interprets sexual deviation.

Classical Commentaries on the Verses was made by several Islamic scholars such as Ibn Kathīr who emphasizes that the people of Lūṭ committed an act unknown among previous nations driven by lust rather than necessity making it even more reprehensible. Al-Qurtubī states that the verses establish the illegality of homosexual acts and that the severe divine punishment that befell the people of Lūṭ stands as a lesson for all latter generations. Fakhr al-Dīn al-Rāzī links the prohibition to the *fiṭrah* (natural disposition) noting that same-sex sexual activity contradicts the biological and psychological complementarity designed by God.

Sunnah offers additional detail beyond the Qur'an by explicitly condemning homosexual acts. *"Whoever you find doing the action of the people of Lūṭ, kill the one who does it and the one to whom it is done."* (Sunan Abī Dāwūd; Jāmi' al-Tirmidhī). Although scholars differ about the chain of narration, classical jurists accepted its meaning as reinforcing the Qur'anic stance.

The Hadith of Curse (La'nah): *"Allah curses the one who does the action of the people of Lūṭ."* (Reported by Ibn Hibbān) and the Hadith on Effeminacy: *"The Prophet cursed men who imitate women and women who imitate men* (Bukhārī 5885) are used by classical scholars to argue that Islamic law discourages gender nonconformity.

IMPLICATIONS OF LGBTQ+ PRACTICES: ISLAMIC PERSPECTIVE

LGBTQ+ is viewed from Islamic perspective from the angle of Islamic law, social moral and ethics, faith. The Islamic classical scholars, generally categorize it under prohibits the acts (same-sex acts) (Wael 2009). The position of Islamic law from the narration and repercussion of Prophet Lut's people's Quranic analysis maintains that same-sex's practice was condemned, rejected and punished by Allah with: destruction by rain of stones(Q11;82-83);

So, when Our command came, We turned it (the town) upside down and rained upon it stones of baked clay, layered, marked from your Lord. Also, destruction of their city where everything went abnormal for the inhabitants (criminals) Q7:84); and with a mighty loud blast; Q15;73). In order to avoid same or more happening to this generation, such prohibited heinous.

In view of the above, social implications include the disruption of Lineage (*Nasab*). Meaning that, it will be difficult to procreate, and multiplication of human generation may go into extinction; hence same-sex marriage. Islamic law places enormous importance on lineage. Same-sex unions disrupt biological procreation, inheritance structures, endowment (*Waqf*) and marital institution in general. Islamic family law is built upon Male-female marriage, complementarity of roles and reproductive continuity. Same-sex unions challenge this foundational unit as they raise conflicts with Guardianship (*wilāyah*), Custody (*ḥaḍānah*) and Lineage-based inheritance. Obviously, male do not possess naturally, female reproductive system. Gasner & Aatasha (2023) described the

uterus and cervix as structures formed from Mullerian ducts and located in the female reproductive tract.

Ethical and Spiritual implications arise also due to the violation of Divine Order. The Qur'an and Sunnah establish heterosexuality as the normative sexual path. Engaging in prohibited acts can harden the heart, block spiritual light, distance one from divine mercy and create inner conflict and guilt.

The Rise of LGBTQ+ Activism in Muslim Societies has Muslims today encounter competing worldviews such as Western liberal individualism against Islamic divine commandments on morality. Muslim scholars argue that moral frameworks must be rooted in revelation not social trends. Nigeria is not only a deeply religious nation but a Muslim-majority region in the North which legally opposes same-sex marriage. The *Shari'ah* states criminalize homosexual acts with varying degrees of punishment. The need for compassionate engagement arises since Islam discourages violence, harassment, vigilantism and humiliation. It promotes Da'wah with wisdom, confidential counseling, spiritual support and rehabilitation as better approaches.

Some modern voices such as Scott Sirajulhaqq Kugle in his book "Homosexuality in Islam", Kecia Ali, Amina Wadud, Junaiad Jahangir, Hussein Abdullatif and Muhsin Hendricks argue that the people of Lūṭ were punished for rape not homosexuality as the Qur'an does not explicitly mention lesbianism and modern sexual identity categories did not exist. They reinterpreted the Qur'anic narrative of the people of Lūṭ as a condemnation of sexual violence, coercion and social injustice rather than consensual same sex relations. However, this position diverges significantly from classical exegetical consensus. Classical responses from scholars include verses explicitly referring to approaching men with desire (*Shahwah*) and the condemnation of *Siḥāq* (lesbian acts) by consensus of jurists as the Shari'ah regulates actions not identity labels and moral rulings do not change due to social evolution.

Islam views sex as sacred, regulated and purposeful for procreation, emotional tranquility, spiritual balance and protection from immorality, preservation of family and continuity of human society which is undermined by same-sex sexual relations. While the act is sinful, Islam emphasizes that no Sin is beyond Allah's forgiveness and repentance (*tawbah*) is always open and no shaming or exposure should be practiced as Islam strictly forbids exposing others sexual sins. No vigilante punishments should be meted out as only the courts can administer punishments in *Shari'ah* governed territories. Finally, every human being regardless of sin deserves respect, protection and justice.

Conclusion

Islamic jurists maintain a clear, consistent and unanimous position with the Qur'an, Sunnah, classical Fiqh and contemporary scholarship that homosexual acts are prohibited while individuals remain deserving of compassion and support. It also distinguishes between inclination and action. Islam's moral framework aims not to punish individuals but to preserve family, lineage, social

stability and spiritual well-being. Muslim societies today must navigate contemporary debates with wisdom, empathy, scholarship and unwavering fidelity to divine revelation. Modern applications highlight the balance between moral firmness and ethical compassion emphasizing counselling, privacy and humane engagement.

Recommendation

Having discussed extensively on the topic, the following five recommendations are made:

- (1) The verdicts and statuesque of the primary sources of Islam must be retained;
- (2) Parents must monitor, train or watch over very closely their children;
- (3) Children must also be careful about their choice of friends and peer group they will associate with;
- (4) There should be a promulgated law that will punish the offenders; and
- (5) All Islamic studies teachers, lecturers, Imams and guardians must be very close observant of their children in other to hinder them from being parties in the game of LGBTQ+

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